

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE ESTABLISHMENT OF AMIR TEMUR'S RELATIONS WITH EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract. This article highlights the importance of relations between Amir Temur and Bayazid for European countries. Amir Temur's invasion of the Middle East and Asia Minor attracted the attention of European countries. It was this attention that later led to the establishment of relations between Amir Temur and European countries.

Key words. Amir Temur, Bayazid. Europe, Asia Minor, France, England, Castile and Lyon, Middle East, embassy.

With the victory of Amir Temur over the Turkish sultan Bayazid I, he completed the "seven-year" campaign and gradually began to move back towards Samarkand. Ambassadors of various countries visited him along the way to congratulate him with victory. At this point, let's focus on the active relations between the state of Amir Temur and the rulers of Western European countries. Amir Temur's relations with the rulers of European countries, as we mentioned above, began earlier. The victory over Bayezid I brought these relations to a new level.

Let's take a look at the history of the establishment of relations between Amir Temur's state and European countries. In the last quarter of the 14th century, the Ottoman state took control of the strait connecting the Aegean Sea and the Black Sea [1]. As a result of this, the relations of European countries with Asia were seriously damaged.

In addition, the actions of the Turks in the Balkans and the crusade organized against them were ineffective, and the Europeans fell into a depressed state. In such a situation, the news about Amir Temur's power and his movement towards the west spread to all of Europe through the state of Trebizond. After that, one after another, European countries began to communicate with Amir Temur.

We can divide the diplomatic relations between the Europeans and Amir Temur into three stages. The first stage - before the battle of Ankara, the second stage - during the battle, the third stage - the last communications after the battle.

Embassy communications before the battle of Ankara were kept secret. The reason for this was the fear of Bayazid by Genoese, Venetians and Byzantines. Some information about these diplomatic relations has been preserved in the accounting documents of Genoa. But the given information is brief and succinct.

In order to establish good relations with Amir Temur, the Byzantine emperor showed great activity. According to Lucien Keren, in 1394 and 1399, a Dominican monk named Francois from Byzantium was an ambassador to Amir Temur twice [1]. When Francois came to Amir Timur for the first time, he told him that if he starts a

military campaign against Bayezid, the countries located in the eastern Mediterranean will help him. However, we have not received any information about how Amir Temur responded to this ambassador.

Francois came on his second mission with a man named Sandro. This time, he told Amir Temur that if he starts a war against Bayezid, he will pay the tribute intended for Bayezid to Amir Temur.

In 1400, ambassadors came to Amir Temur from Venice. This embassy was headed by Andrea Justinian and Mateo Barbadigo. As a result of this embassy, good relations were established between Amir Temur's state and Venice.

In August 1401, Amir Temur's ambassadors went to Genoa. This was based on the information written in the account book of a person originally from Pera.

According to the account book in Pera, from May 18 to June 21, 1402, the ambassador of Amir Temur came here [1].

We must say that the victory of Amir Temur next to Ankara decided the fate of Europe. Because the ambassadors of the French king Charles VI, the Byzantine emperor Manuel II, the Pope of Rome, Venice, and Henry III, the king of Castile and Leon, carefully watched the battle here.

The reason why the battle between Amir Temur and Bayezid did not leave European countries indifferent was the victorious campaigns of the Turks in South-Eastern and Eastern Europe. Because the success of the Ottomans in this area was considered as a real problem for European countries that had not yet been fully centralized. In particular, as a confirmation of our opinion, we can cite the fact that in 1396 knights from several European countries were defeated by Turkish janissaries [2]. From this we can conclude that the European countries were not yet strong enough to withstand the Ottoman army.

In addition to Byzantium, Venice and Genoa, ambassadors from Castile, France and other countries of Western Europe also visited Amir Temur. Among these countries, Castile treated Amir Temur and Bayazid differently than others. Therefore, in 1402, King Henry III sent his ambassadors Payo de Sotomayor and Hernán Sánchez de Palazuelos to Asia Minor. The purpose of the ambassadors was to know the military power of Bayazid and Amir Temur, to determine their attitude towards Europe. These ambassadors first went to the reception of Bayazid I in May 1402, and after the victory near Ankara, they went to the reception of Amir Temur.

Amir welcomed the Spanish ambassadors who came to Temur. He sent them to his country along with gifts and greetings, accompanied by his ambassador Muhammad al-Keshi.

King Henry III of Castile and Leon, who wanted to establish good relations with Amir Timur, sent ambassadors led by Rui González de Clavijo to him in response to this embassy. The embassy headed by Claviho reached Samarkand in September 1404 [5]. Claviho visited many cities during his trip to Samarkand. When he came to each city, he paid special attention to the environment there. Along the way, Amir gathered

interesting information about Temur from each other. The historical significance of this mission is that Clavijo wrote down his journey as a souvenir. His memoirs were published in 1582 by Argote de Molina under the title "History of Temurlang the Great". For a long time, a large part of Europeans had an understanding of Amir Temur based on the information in this work.

Amir Temur's victory in the battle near Ankara brought him closer to European countries. The entrepreneur tried to establish good relations with European countries and focused on establishing trade relations between the countries.

On September 2, 1402, two representatives from Constantinople - Podestat Bartolomeo Ross and his companion Jano Lomellino - came to Amir Temur [3]. They discussed the main issue, the tribute to be paid to Amir Temur.

After the Battle of Ankara, despite being involved in the Hundred Years War, England and France established diplomatic relations through correspondence with the country of Amir Temur. In particular, the correspondence between Amir Temur and King Charles VI of France has been preserved to this day. Amir Temur sent his name to Charles VI on August 1, 1402 through ambassadors headed by Archbishop John. This embassy visited Paris in June 1403[1]. The ambassadors stayed in Paris for a month, received the reply letter and returned on July 15 of this year. The main purpose of this exchange of letters was to establish trade relations between the countries.

There was also an exchange of letters between Amir Temur and King Henry IV of England. Archbishop Ioan played a major role in this embassy as well. Two letters of King Henry of England to Amir Temur and Mironshah have been preserved. The date of John's ambassadorship to England is uncertain, but it is believed to have been between 1399 and 1404.

King Henry of England had a good relationship with Mironshah. Recognizing Mironshah as the patron of the Catholic religion, he did not hide his satisfaction with the establishment of trade relations between the two countries. In addition, in his letter to Amir Temur, he expressed his satisfaction with the victory over the common enemy, the Turks.

Amir Temur's victory over Bayezid gained great importance in the history of Italy as well as other European countries. Two Italian states, Genoa and Venice, were considered the main enemies of the Ottoman Empire. If Amir Temur had not won against Bayazid, it became clear that these two Italian countries would have waged war against the Turks at this time. If the war took place at the time of discussion, it was inevitable that it would bring negative consequences for Italy, which is considered the homeland of the European renaissance. Taking this into account, Amir Temur's victory over the Ottomans paved the way for the renaissance to develop in Europe.

List of used literature

1. Амир Темур жаҳон тарихида. / Муҳаррирлар: Ҳ. Нурмухамедов ва бошқ. – Париж–Т.: Шарқ, 1996.

2. Amoretti B.S. Religion in the Timurid and Sefarid periods / The Cambridge history of Iran, Vol. VI. Charter 12, 1956.
3. Keren L. Tamerlan. Paris. 1980.
4. Law and Phorson Berwick W. The History of the life of Tamerlane the Great / Paris. 1782.
5. Руи Гонсалес де Клавихо. Самарқандга Амир Темур саройига саёҳат кундалиги (1403-1406-йиллар). Рус тилидан О. Тогаев таржимаси. Масъул муҳаррир Муҳаммад Али. Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон”, 2010.